

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20422903>

IKKINCHI TARTIBLI INTEGRO-DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR UCHUN TESKARI MASALALAR

Raxmonov Bo‘ron Normamatovich

Axborot texnologiyalari va menejment universiteti dotsenti

buronr@inbox.ru

Qo‘chqorov Alimardon Hoshim o‘g‘li

Axborot texnologiyalari va menejment universiteti 2-kurs magistranti

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada chegaraviy shartda spektral parametrga polinom ko‘rinishida bog‘liq bo‘lgan ikkinchi tartibli Sturm–Liuvill turidagi integro-differensial operatorlar qaraladi. Tadqiqotda teskari masala o‘rganilib, u o‘z qiymatlar hamda chegaraviy shartdagi ikkita ma‘lum polinom yordamida konvolyutsiya yadrosi va chegaraviy shartdagi noma‘lum polinomlardan birini tiklashdan iborat. Mazkur masalaning yechimi yagonaligi isbotlanadi. Bundan tashqari, teskari masalani yechish uchun konstruktiv algoritmi ishlab chiqiladi hamda masalaning yechilishi uchun zarur va yetarli shartlar aniqlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar. *Integro-differensial tenglama, Sturm–Liuvill masalasi, teskari masala, spektral parametr, konvolyutsiya yadrosi, chegaraviy shart, o‘z qiymatlar, operatorlar puchogi, spektral tahlil.*

Kirish. So‘nggi yillarda integro-differensial tenglamalar va ular bilan bog‘liq teskari masalalarni o‘rganish matematik fizika, mexanika hamda muhandislik sohalarida muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Bunday tenglamalar ko‘plab fizik

jarayonlarni, jumladan issiqlik o'tkazuvchanligi, tebranishlar nazariyasi, to'qlinlar tarqalishi va boshqaruv tizimlarini modellashtirishda keng qo'llaniladi.

Sturm–Liuvill turidagi masalalar spektral nazariyada muhim o'rin egallaydi. Ayniqsa, spektral parametrning chegaraviy shartlarda ishtirok etishi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan integro-differensial operatorlar puchogi ko'plab amaliy masalalarda uchraydi. Bunday masalalarda asosiy muammolardan biri berilgan spektral ma'lumotlar yordamida operatorning noma'lum elementlarini tiklashdan iborat bo'lgan teskari masalalarni yechishdir.

Mazkur ishda spektral parametrga polinom ko'rinishida bog'liq bo'lgan chegaraviy shartli ikkinchi tartibli Sturm–Liuvill turidagi integro-differensial operatorlar puchogi qaraladi. Teskari masala o'z qiymatlar va chegaraviy shartdagi ikkita ma'lum polinom yordamida konvolyutsiya yadrosi hamda noma'lum polinomni aniqlashdan iborat. Ishda masalaning yechimi yagonaligi isbotlanadi, shuningdek uni yechish uchun konstruktiv algoritmi ishlab chiqiladi va masalaning yechilish shartlari aniqlanadi.

Integro-differensial operatorlar uchun teskari masalalar bo'yicha dastlabki parcha-parcha natijalar [6-7] ishlarida yoritilgan. Keyinchalik turli differensial operatorlarning konvolyutsion buzilishlarini tiklash uchun kuchli metod ishlab chiqildi. Ushbu metod teskari masalani maxsus ko'rinishdagi yagona yechimga ega bo'lgan nolinear tenglamaga keltirishga asoslanadi. Yaqinda bunday nolinear tenglamalarning umumiy nazariyasi [3] ishida ishlab chiqilgan. Integro-differensial operatorlar uchun teskari masalalarning boshqa turlari esa [4–5] ishlarda o'rganilgan.

Faraz qilaylik, bizda ikki o'lchovli integro-differensial tenglama mavjud:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u(x, y)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u(x, y)}{\partial y^2} + \int_0^x \int_0^y K(x, y, s, t) u(s, t) ds dt = \lambda u(x, y)$$

bu yerda: $u(x, y)$ - noma'lum funksiya, $K(x, y, s, t)$ - berilgan yadro yoki integral operatorning kerneli, λ - spektral parameter.

Teorema. Masala L ning spektri xos qiymatlardan iborat sanaladigan to'plam bo'lib, u quyidagi ko'rinishda ifodalanishi mumkin:

$$\Lambda = \{\lambda_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \cup \{\tilde{\lambda}_j\}_{j=1}^n$$

Faraz qilaylik $\Lambda = \{\lambda_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \cup \{\tilde{\lambda}_j\}_{j=1}^n$ — har qanday kompleks sonlar ketma-ketligi, u asimptotik munosabat mos kelsin, va $A_j(\lambda)$, $j=1,2$ -darajasi n bo'lgan polinomlar bo'lib, ularning kompleks koeffitsiyentlariga ega.

Chegaraviy shartlar sifatida: $u(0, y) = u(a, y) = u(x, 0) = u(x, b) = 0$ ni olamiz bu yerda $(x, y) \in [0, a] \times [0, b]$.

Yuqoridagi boshlang'ich shartlardan foydalanib teskari masalani qo'yamiz agar bizga spektral qiymat $\{\lambda_{mn}\}$ ko'rinishda berilgan bo'lsa, u holda $K(x, y, s, t)$ yadro quyidagicha ifodalanadi. Bizga to'plam $\{\lambda_{mn}\}$ va ba'zi cheklangan shakldagi kernel polinomial yoki separabl deb belgilasak,

$$K(x, y, s, t) = M(x, y)N(s, t) \text{ yoki } K(x, y, s, t) = \sum_{ij} c_{ij} \phi_i(x) \psi_j(y) \phi_i(s) \psi_j(t) \text{ yadro}$$

ko'rinishga keladi, bu yerda ϕ_i, ψ_j - ortogonal bazis funksiyalar hisoblanadi.

Chegaraviy shartlar bo'yicha, klassik Sturm–Liuvill metodiga asoslanib, funksiya $u(x, y)$ ni ajratish mumkin:

$$u_{mn}(x, y) = \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{b}\right), m, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

bo'lsa, u holda spertrial tenglamani quyidagicha ifodalaymiz.

$$\lambda_{mn} = \left(\frac{m\pi}{a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{n\pi}{b}\right)^2 + \int_0^a \int_0^b K(x, y, s, t) u_{mn}(s, t) ds dt = u_{mn}(x, y)$$

Agar K separabl bo'lsa, integral hisoblari soddalashadi:

$$\int_0^a \int_0^b M(x, y) N(s, t) u_{mn}(s, t) ds dt = M(x, y) \int_0^a \int_0^b N(s, t) u_{mn}(s, t) ds dt$$

ko'rinishga keladi.

Spektral parametr xossalaridan foydalanib, kernel parametrlarini quyidagicha ifodalaymiz. Agar kernel koeffitsiyentlari c_{ij} bilan ifodalansa, har bir λ_{mn} quyidagi ko'rinishga ega:

$$\lambda_{mn} = \lambda_{mn}^{(0)} + \sum_{i,j} c_{ij} \alpha_{mn}^{ij}$$

bu yerda $\lambda_{mn}^{(0)} = \left(\frac{m\pi}{a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{n\pi}{b}\right)^2$, α_{mn}^{ij} esa integral hisoblar natijasi. Bu

tenglamalar chiziqli tizimni hosil qiladi c_{ij} ni topish uchun.

Agar K yadroni soddalashtirib 4 ta koeffitsientli shaklda ifodalasak

$$K(x, y, s, t) = c_{11}\phi_1\psi_1 + c_{12}\phi_1\psi_2 + c_{21}\phi_2\psi_1 + c_{22}\phi_2\psi_2$$

unda har bir xos qiymat uchun tenglama hosil bo'ladi.

Masalan:

(1,1) spektr uchun

$$\lambda_{11} - \lambda_{11}^{(0)} = c_{11}\alpha_{11}^{11} + c_{12}\alpha_{11}^{12} + c_{21}\alpha_{11}^{21} + c_{22}\alpha_{11}^{22}$$

(1,2) spektr uchun

$$\lambda_{12} - \lambda_{12}^{(0)} = c_{11}\alpha_{12}^{11} + c_{12}\alpha_{12}^{12} + c_{21}\alpha_{12}^{21} + c_{22}\alpha_{12}^{22}$$

(2,1) spektr uchun

$$\lambda_{21} - \lambda_{21}^{(0)} = c_{11}\alpha_{21}^{11} + c_{12}\alpha_{21}^{12} + c_{21}\alpha_{21}^{21} + c_{22}\alpha_{21}^{22}$$

(2,2) spektr uchun

$$\lambda_{22} - \lambda_{22}^{(0)} = c_{11}\alpha_{22}^{11} + c_{12}\alpha_{22}^{12} + c_{21}\alpha_{22}^{21} + c_{22}\alpha_{22}^{22}$$

Bu tenglamada quyidagi chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi hosil bo'ladi.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{11}^{11} & \alpha_{11}^{12} & \alpha_{11}^{21} & \alpha_{11}^{22} \\ \alpha_{12}^{11} & \alpha_{12}^{12} & \alpha_{12}^{21} & \alpha_{12}^{22} \\ \alpha_{21}^{11} & \alpha_{21}^{12} & \alpha_{21}^{21} & \alpha_{21}^{22} \\ \alpha_{22}^{11} & \alpha_{22}^{12} & \alpha_{22}^{21} & \alpha_{22}^{22} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{11} \\ c_{12} \\ c_{21} \\ c_{22} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_{11} - \lambda_{11}^{(0)} \\ \lambda_{12} - \lambda_{12}^{(0)} \\ \lambda_{21} - \lambda_{21}^{(0)} \\ \lambda_{22} - \lambda_{22}^{(0)} \end{pmatrix}$$

Tenglamalar sistemasining yechimi, agar determinant nolga teng bo'lmasa: $\det A \neq 0$ bo'lsa, tenglamalar sistemasining yechimi $C = A^{-1} \cdot B$ ko'rinishda topiladi.

Operatorlarning yangi sinfi, ya'ni spektral parametrga nolchiziqli bog'liq bo'lgan integro-differensial tenglamalar ko'rib chiqiladi. Biz integral tenglamalarga ega Sturm–Liuvill tenglamasi uchun chegaraviy masalalarini qaradik[6].

Chegaraviy shartlari spektral parametr ga polinomial bog‘liq bo‘lgan Sturm–Liuvill turidagi differensial operator pencillari uchun teskari masalalarni tadqiq qilish oddiy differensial operatorlarga nisbatan ancha murakkabliklarni keltirib chiqaradi.

Ushbu maqola integro-differensial operatorlar uchun teskari masalalar nazariyasiga bag‘ishlangan. Spektral tahlildagi teskari masalalar operatorlarni ularning spektral xarakteristikalarini orqali qayta tiklashdan iborat [7]. Teskari masalalar nazariyasining asosiy natijalari asosan differensial operatorlar uchun olingan. Hozirgi kunda nolokal operatorlar, xususan integro-differensial operatorlar matematiklar e‘tiborini tobora ko‘proq jalb qilmoqda. Bir tomondan, bunday operatorlar fizika, biologiya, muhandislik va boshqa amaliy sohalaridagi real jarayonlarni modellashtirish uchun tabiiy vosita hisoblanadi [5]. Boshqa tomondan, integro-differensial operatorlarning nolokal xususiyati teskari masalalar nazariyasining klassik usullari uchun jiddiy to‘siq bo‘lib xizmat qiladi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. S. A. Buterin, The inverse problem of recovering the Volterra convolution operator from the incomplete spectrum of its rank-one perturbation, *Inverse Problems*, 22 (2006), 2223–2236.
2. S. A. Buterin, On an inverse spectral problem for a convolution integro-differential operator, *Results Math.*, 50 (2007), no.3-4, 73–181.
3. N. Bondarenko and S. Buterin, On recovering the Dirac operator with an integral delay from the spectrum, *Results Math.*, 71 (2017), 1521–1529
4. Yu. V. Kuryshova and C.-T. Shieh, An inverse nodal problem for integro-differential operators, *J. Inverse IllPosed Prob.* 18(2010), 357–369.
5. Y. Wang and G. Wei, The uniqueness for Sturm–Liouville problems with aftereffect, *Acta Math. Sci.*, 32A(2012), 1171–1178.
6. B. Keskin and A. S. Ozkan, Inverse nodal problems for Dirac-type integro-differential operators, *Journal of Differential Equations*, 63 (2017), 8838–8847

7. Normamatovich, R. B. (2025). DASTURIY VOSITALAR ORQALI IKKI ZARRACHALI SHRYODINGER OPERATORINING DISKRET XOS QIYMATLARINI TADQIQ QILISH. *IZLANUVCHI*, 2(3), 21-27.